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Spectrophotometric Determination of Cobalt with Furoin Thiosemicarbazone[®]

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NUMEROUS reagents have been reported for the spectrophotometric determination of cobalt which include 1-nitroso-2 naphthol and thiocyanate¹, benzamidoxime², metidan³ and thioglycerol⁴. Recently thiosemicarbazones of picolinaldehyde⁵ and di-2 pyridylketone⁶ are reported as reagents for the determination of various metal ions such as cobalt, nickel, iron and copper. The reported methods either require elaborate experimental procedure or complexes are less stable in aqueous medium. In this paper we propose furoin thiosemicarbazone as a new spectrophotometric reagent which has considerably high stability in aqueous medium. The procedure is simple and the interference due to several ions may be easily removed.

Experimental

Reagent

Ethanollic 10% solution of furoin (5 m mole) and aqueous 20% solution of thiosemicarbazide (20 m mole) were mixed in presence of 2-3 drops of anhydrous acetic acid and refluxed for two hours. The yellowish crystals of furoin thiosemicarbazone appeared on cooling were recrystallized twice from hot (1 : 1) ethanol.

0.25% (w/v) solution of furoin thiosemicarbazone was prepared in (1 : 1) methanol. The reagent solution is stable for at least two months.

Cobalt solution

A stock solution (1 mg ml⁻¹) of cobalt(II) ion was prepared by dissolving cobalt sulphate heptahydrate in double distilled water and was standardized gravimetrically⁷.

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Reagent grade chemicals were used throughout.

Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer with 10 mm matched glass cuvettes was used for measuring the absorbance. pH was monitored with Philips PR 9405L pH meter with glass and calomel electrodes. pH values of the solutions were adjusted by dil. hydrochloric acid or ammonia solutions.

General procedure

An aliquot of sample solution containing up to 10 ppm of cobalt was taken and excess (20 times) reagent was added. The pH was adjusted to 7.5 and the solution was diluted to 25 ml in standard flask with distilled water. The optical density of the cobalt complex was measured at 365 nm against reagent blank prepared in the same manner excluding cobalt. The concentration of cobalt in the unknown solution was found out from standard calibration curve obtained under identical conditions.

Results and Discussion

Investigation of the spectra

The spectra of furoin thiosemicarbazone : cobalt systems were run over a wide range of pH values which show an absorption band with $\lambda_{\max}$ at 365 nm. The extinction coefficient at 365 nm and at pH 7.5 is 8095 l mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Absorption spectrum of the Co(II)-Complex(B), and the ligand (A)

(B): Co(II) : $6.792 \times 10^{-5} M$ and ligand : $6.887 \times 10^{-3} M$
(A): Ligand : $6.887 \times 10^{-3} M$

Beer's law and physical constants

Beer's law was valid up to 10 ppm of cobalt. The Sandell sensitivity of the reaction as calculated from Beer's plot is found to be $0.00727 \mu\text{g Co cm}^{-2}$ at 365 nm for $\log I_0/I=0.001$. The molar extinction coefficient of the complex is $8095 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The Ringbom's plot indicated that the optimum range is 1.6 to $5.0 \mu\text{g Co ml}^{-1}$.

Effect of pH

A series of solutions varying in pH from 3 to 12 were prepared and the absorbances were recorded at 365 nm. It was observed that no change in absorbance took place over the pH range 7 to 8. The absorbance of the solutions decreases at higher or lower pH values. The pH 7.5 was maintained in further studies.

Effect of reagent concentration

It was observed that 0.75 ml of the reagent solution is adequate for colour development. However twice the amount was used to ensure full colour development. The reagent has negligible absorbance at the wavelength selected for measurement.

Composition of the complex

Job's method of continuous variation⁸ was studied. Solutions were mixed in different proportions keeping the total molarity constant. The curve obtained indicates the formation of cobalt complex in which the metal : ligand ratio is 1 : 2. This conclusion is supported by the mole ratio⁹ and slope ratio¹⁰⁻¹¹ methods.

Effect of diverse ions

The solutions containing known amounts of cobalt and varying amounts of diverse ions were prepared and cobalt was determined in their presence. It was observed that large number of cations such as Ti^{3+} , UO_2^{2+} , Mo^{6+} , Zn^{2+} , V^{5+} , Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Re^{6+} , Ce^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Pb^{2+} , In^{3+} can be tolerated in the ratio of at least 1 : 20. Fairly large number of anions like SO_4^{2-} , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, HCO_3^- , HCOO^- , HC_2O_4^- , tartrate are tolerated in large amounts. Nickel ion shows strong interference and must be absent. Interference of copper can be avoided by prior separation¹². Fluoride ion can be used as masking agent for Mn(II) and Fe(III) up to 30 ppm.

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Oxazine Dyes as New Iodometric Indicators[†]

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IN a continuation of our work on the use of oxazine dyes as indicators¹⁻⁴, we have found that eight oxazine dyes, Capri Blue(CPB), Meldola's Blue (MB), Celestine Blue(CLB), Gallamine Blue(GB), Solochrome Prune AS(SPAS), Brilliant Cresyl Blue (BCB) (Colour Index Nos. 51015, 51175, 51050, 51045, 51040 and 51010 respectively), Cresyl Fast Violet Acetate(CFVA), and Resazurin(RSZ) (the structures of these dyes are given below), can be used as indicators in the direct and reverse titrations of iodine with thiosulphate, arsenic(III), ascorbic acid, hydrazine, mercaptoacetic acid and uric acid. The advantages of these indicators are : their solubility in cold water and stability of their aqueous solutions. In this connection, it may be mentioned that till now very few indicators have been reported for the titration of ascorbic acid⁵⁻⁸ and hydrazine⁹ with iodine, and apart from starch, no other indicator has been proposed for the uric acid-iodine titration⁹.

The indicator methods now developed have been utilised for the determination of ascorbic acid content of commercial vitamin C tablets and some fruit

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